

Sustainability, Integrated Development, And Future Prospects For Arab World Communities Design Of Education Facilities Spaces During Pandemic Outbreak

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Abstract

The World is suffering from pollutions and sick buildings. Moreover because of COVID 19, most of the countries around the world introduced national preventative measures to slow the spread of the deadly virus by announcing the closure of schools and higher education institutions, and the commitment of online learning.

The stuff suddenly were facing the challenge of teaching design through distance learning approach and as an educators of interior design, we were part of the team tasked to find ways to teach design without physical contact with the students nor access to campus facilities traditionally used to run the program and its associated courses. The same challenge was at schools, While COVID-19 has shuttered school and university buildings coast-to-coast and globally, some things remain. There is the keen anticipation of students, educators and staff members to return to their schools, where there will be a need, at least for some time, for social distancing, stepped-up cleaning and other practices.

Responses to COVID-19 may continue to extend the classroom virtually for some time and in greater numbers than before the pandemic, but it is unclear precisely how and to what extent that may occur in university and schools institutions.

now a days the universities and schools are trying to back teaching face to face where the challenge is to achieve safe environments in the class rooms was the big concern ,with the above said the aim of the research is to find an interior design solutions to solve this problems and to safe the users.

In this research we will introduce the applications status of domestic and foreign anti-bacterial materials in furniture and interior Designs for the Education Facilities spaces as an interior design solution during Pandemic outbreak, including the application status and developing trends of antibacterial furniture, antibacterial floor, and anti-bacterial glass.

Research problem:

- *Lack of studies on the impact of modern and technological materials, in the Education Facilities spaces during pandemic outbreak.*

Importance of the research:

- *Identification of the modern technological methods of materials and their applications on the Education Facilities spaces during pandemic outbreak.*
- *Highlighting innovative solutions for modern materials and their design applications on the Education Facilities spaces during pandemic outbreak.*

Research objective:

- *Finding innovative solutions for modern materials' technology and their applications on the Education Facilities spaces during pandemic outbreak.*
- *Utilization of various materials and development of designs that are environmentally compatible in the Education Facilities spaces during pandemic outbreak.*

Introduction

Innovation is of great importance in our lives, it is of utmost necessity in our time, due to the role of the higher levels of thinking and innovation in changing history and reshaping the real world, in line with the renewed needs and complexity of life societies cannot be changed easily, only The members of the community owe innovation to change, develop and sustain the dynamism of the society. The relationship between innovation and development is inextricably linked, with the burden of innovation on the development and progress of society. (1)

Health care Materials:

Materials create different effects on humans with their physical, mechanical and formal properties, for example surface qualities. For healthcare interiors, Physical properties such as safety, capacity for easy cleaning, maintenance, and appropriateness for different users can be listed as the main parameters.(2)

Alternative Materials:

Recycling: Recycling refers to the process in which an element or its components are used to create something new. Technically recycling is a form of reuse but more specifically refers to the

1-<https://ar.wikipedia.org/wiki/تكنولوجيا>

2-Cigdem Cetin* Zeynep Tuna Ultav† The Effects of Interior Design Parameters on the Design Quality of Nurse Stations Athens Journal of Architecture - Volume 4, Issue 2– Pages 149-170: P:156

Elements that are disposed of and divided into their raw materials. The original item into a product and then sell items that can be used immediately. (1)

The psychological impact of privacy during pandemic outbreak:

Privacy in general is the right of individuals, groups, organization, and institutions to determine for themselves especially during pandemic out break when, how and to what extent information about them is communicated to others. In a public space, there is no restriction of communication, while isolated spaces completely constrain all types of communication. In between there are intermediate levels of privacy. Space privacy is considered one of the most important types of overall privacy.

"According to environmental psychology, each person is realized and perceived through an invisible shelter or a series of shelters surrounding his body, Figure 5-1. These personal protective spheres, by which privacy is controlled, vary from person to person and from culture to culture. They also differ from period to period as society and social bonds are continually transformed and reconstructed.(2)

The science of controlling infections during pandemic outbreak:

Caused by airborne microorganisms is a complex mixture of engineering, particle physics, microbiology, and medicine. The rates at which particles settle are a function of their size, shape, density, and of course, air movement. Turbulence within a room increases the residence time of larger particles in the air, hence the desire for laminar airflows in Classrooms rooms.

Some of the ways that potentially infectious microorganisms can be spread in a health care environment include:(3)

- 1- sneezes and coughs,
- 2- Inhalation,
- 3- Contact,
- 4- Water mist
- 5- Insect bite

1-Hussein Mirna Mohammed - Design for recycling as one of the environmental requirements in product design - Journal of Architecture and Arts - Issue XI - C2 - p 714

2-Heba-Talla Hamdy Mahmoud 1-Interior Architectural Elements that Affect Human Psychology and Behavior- International Journal on: The Academic Research Community Publication-p:4-<http://www.ierek.com/press>

3-Reg Brown, P.E, Nicolas Lemire, P.Eng and others -HVAC Design Manual for Hospitals and Clinics- Second Edition- This publication was prepared under the auspices of ASHRAE Technical Committee (TC) 9.6, Healthcare Facilities p:7-2013

6-Airborne transmission via aerosols is important in some respiratory diseases. Aerosols are particularly dangerous because their size (1 to 5 μm) allows them to be drawn deep into the lungs and retained. Turbulent air may also spread large particles from contaminated soil or from objects such as clothing and floors.

Infection occurs when all of the following elements are present:

- An infectious agent,
- A source of the agent,

A susceptible host to receive the agent

, and most critically, a way for the agent to be transmitted from the source to the host. The interaction among these elements is known as the “chain of infection,” or “disease transmission cycle,” terminology that emphasizes the necessary linkages among all elements. Generally, the severity of the impact of exposure to microorganisms is described by the following relationship: $\text{Infection} = \text{Dose} \times \text{Site} \times \text{Virulence} \times \text{Time}$

Level of Host Defense

Thus, the severity of the impact on persons exposed is determined by the length of the exposure, virulence of the microbes to which they are exposed, location of the exposure, and quantity of microorganisms;(1)

Interior Designs solutions to achieve safety during pandemic outbreak:

1. Materials solutions :

A. Antibacterial Melamine decorative panel:

Properties Economical decorative panel ready to use. Good scratch resistance and clean ability.

Aesthetic quality (edging, surface appearance) and MDF strength (Brown or Black).

Decorative on both sides. Food safe (IANESCO approved).

PEFC™ certified. Silver ion-treated, antibacterial Sanitized® grade.

1-Reg Brown, P.E, Nicolas Lemire, P.Engand others -HVAC Design Manual for Hospitals and Clinics- Second Edition- This publication was prepared under the auspices of ASHRAE Technical Committee (TC) 9.6, Healthcare Facilities p:20,22-2013

• **Applications:**

Suitable for vertical use (partitions) and moderate horizontal use (furniture) in low-traffic environments. Available in moisture resistant grade for humid environments. Panoprey / Polyrey HPL / Compact Reysipur / Polyprey complementary products for harmonious interior design applications.

• **CHARACTERISTICS:**

Function	cover, furniture
Applications	for furniture, for partition walls, for kitchens, for joinery

Technical characteristics	ire-retardant, water-repellent, antibacterial
Finish	textured, matte, high-gloss, satin
Appearance	wood look
Other characteristics	PEFC-certified
Thickness	Min.: 8 mm (0.3 in) Max.: 30 mm (1.2 in)
Width	207 cm (81 in)
Length	280 cm (110 in)

[HTTPS://WWW.ARCHIEXPO.COM/PROD/LAMINAM/PRODUCT-70801-2231686.HTML](https://www.archiexpo.com/prod/laminam/product-70801-2231686.html)

B. Antibacterial Aluminum decorative panel:

- Main applications: Wall cladding Ceiling cladding Door cladding Partition Mirror,Splashback.

• **CHARACTERISTICS:**

Material	aluminum, composite
Applications	for false ceilings, for partition walls
Technical characteristics	antibacterial
Finish	smooth, textured, printed, perforated, lacquered, mirror, stone

Appearance	wood look, stone look, metal look, concrete look
Other characteristics	curved
Company:	Arconic Architectural Products SAS, Merxheim/Frank-UAE

<https://www.archiexpo.com/prod/arconic-architectural-products-sas-merxheim-frank/product-67104-1610515.html>

C. Antibacterial Polymer decorative panel

- **DESCRIPTION:** All the covering strips on the Pure Health baseboards, corner guards, edge protectors and the handrails have had the revolutionary titanium dioxide molecule added which, through the photocatalytic activity stimulated by sunlight or by special lamps, is capable of eliminating 99% of viruses, bacteria and moulds, providing a continuous, fast and effective self-sanitizing action. Disinfection with TiO₂ is in fact three times more effective than chlorine, 1.5 times more than ozone and requires no human intervention.

Material	polymer
Applications	wall-mounted
Technical characteristics	antibacterial
Finish	colored
Company:	Pure Health -Spain

<https://www.archiexpo.com/prod/pure-health/product-153885-1817573.html>

D. Antibacterial Floors:

- **DESCRIPTION:**
- **PVC flooring:** POP Floor is ideal for covering walls and floors in medical environments (operating theatres, emergency rooms, dental surgeries, medical surgeries, waiting rooms, veterinary clinics, etc.) and for creating all the types of seating that may be present in these environments (chairs, beds, sofas, etc.). Conductive POP Floor has also been created for operating theatres with a carbon structure. Pure Health POP Floor is also suitable for any area that needs continuous cleaning and sanitization, such as cold rooms, places where food is stored, schools, gyms, fitness centers, swimming pools, locker rooms, spas.
- **CHARACTERISTICS**

Material	PVC, polyurethane
Options	antibacterial, conductive
Format	strip
Appearance	wood look, stone look
Company	Pure Health -Spain

- <https://www.archiexpo.com/prod/pure-health/product-153885-1816995.html>

E. Antibacterial glass™ by AGC Glass Europe:

- **DESCRIPTION:** Is a major innovation in the world of glass design? The antimicrobial action of the silver ions inside the glass eliminates 99% of all bacteria that form on its surface whilst also preventing the spread of fungi. This remarkable property makes it perfect for places where strict hygiene is a must. Five seconds' contact is enough to pick up 99% of bacteria from a contaminated surface;
- **ANTIBACTERIAL GLASS™ OPERATION AND PERFORMANCE:**
The process developed and patented by AGC Glass Europe involves diffusing silver ions into the upper layers of the glass: the ions interact with bacteria and destroy them by disabling their metabolism and disrupting their division mechanism. The antibacterial effect of the glass is ongoing, particularly in warm and moist conditions favoring the development of bacteria and mould.
- **PERFORMANCE TESTS:**
To evaluate the performance of Antibacterial glass™, tests have been conducted on a representative range of bacteria and fungi:
 1. Bacteria • Staphylococcus Aureus • Escherichia Coli • Pseudomonas Aeruginosa
 2. Fungi • Aspergillus Niger • Candida Albicans.

The bacteria tested on AB glass are found mainly in hospitals and are particularly responsible for nosocomial infections.

- **AGC Glass Europe's Antibacterial glass™ range comprises five products:**

- a) **PLANIBEL AB:** clear glass.
- b) **LACOBEL AB*:** painted glasses.
- c) **MIROX AB*:** mirrors
- d) **STRATOBEL AB:** laminated glass.
- e) **STRATOPHONE AB:** acoustic laminated glass.
- f) Antibacterial glass™ is stamped with a special mark (see logo opposite) certifying it as AB.
- g) For extra safety a polypropylene SAFE+ film can be placed on the painted side of Lacobel AB and Mirox AB.

- **ANTIBACTERIAL GLASS™ applications:**

- a) Lacobel or Mirox AB* is ideal for wall covering in places that are: - subject to specific hygiene requirements:
- b) Hospitals, hematology, oncology and geriatric units, isolation rooms, burns units, sterilisation rooms, etc.
- c) clinics, infirmaries, maternity units • pharmacies and laboratories
- d) Rest homes.
- e) Showers and bathrooms • health spas • sports halls • swimming pools, etc.
- f) Others: • canteens, toilets, etc. • waiting rooms, etc.

- **ANTIBACTERIAL GLASS™ properties:**

- a) **For extra safety a polypropylene SAFE+ film** can be placed on the painted side of Lacobel AB and Mirox AB.
- b) **EASY TO MAINTAIN Antibacterial glass™** is easy to clean and is resistant to cleaning products, including those used in hospitals. Tests have shown that even abrasive maintenance products do not impede the glass's antimicrobial effect.
- c) **EASY TO FIT Fitting AntiBacterial glass™** is easy. Installation techniques differ depending on the product chosen. Please refer to the installation guides for products available in AB (Lacobel, Planibel, Mirox, Stratobel and Stratophone).

<https://www.agc-yourglass.com/>

2. **Improve Air Quality:**

Indoor air is made up of about 25% outside air. The rest is recirculated and filtered, which means it's already been breathed by other occupants. If indoor air is not regularly exchanged, it can actually contain greater levels of pollutants than outside air, according to studies by the Environmental Protection Agency. Natural ventilation systems are an efficient way to flush out the bad and bring in the good air. In private office settings, indoor air pollutants, including bacteria, can build up quickly, so experts recommend at least four air exchanges per hour. Unfortunately, incorporating natural ventilation systems for a large office building is not always practical — although some, like The Tower at PNC Plaza in Pittsburgh, are in a location where natural ventilation makes sense for much of the year.

<https://www.gensler.com/research-insight/blog/designing-office-building-lobbies-to-respond-to-coronavirus>.

- **Filtration:**

- In rooms or operating rooms, sick people have their immune system at its weakest, making your body vulnerable to bacteria, viruses and other airborne infections. HVAC systems that use HEPA filtration can capture infectious particles, control bacteria and prevent the spread of airborne diseases to your most sensitive patients. However, without continuous monitoring and maintenance, including filter replacement and cleaning of heat exchangers, pockets of infection can occur. For this reason, the requirement to maintain the installation in perfect condition and extend the life of these elements must also be taken into account. Such precise systems also require adequate and continuous maintenance. Keeping the filters clean and in good condition, verifying the water tightness from time to time, and checking the differential pressure measurement elements between the different points, can be vital, because it would avoid that areas that must be protected keep the heat exchange batteries clean and the implementation of rigorous maintenance programs of cooling towers if they exist or of the ducts are only some of the ways in which HVAC systems prevent the appearance of risks.

- <https://www.keyter.com/la-importancia-de-los-sistemas-hvac-en-los-hospitales/>

Interior architectural considerations for functionality and flexibility in the Education Facilities spaces during pandemic outbreak.

Interior designs solutions during pandemic outbreak Examples (Schools):

1-Den Bosch, Netherlands by using clear Plexiglas dividers:

Pupils sitting behind partition boards made of plexiglass attend a class at a primary school, during the coronavirus disease (COVID-19) outbreak, in Den Bosch, Netherlands, May 8, 2020. REUTERS/Piroschka van de Wouw TPX IMAGES OF THE DAY.

<https://www.reuters.com/article/us-health-coronavirus-netherlands-school/plastic-shields-in-place-dutch-schools-to-reopen-amid-coronavirus-idUSKBN22K242>

-School Pupils in china by using acrylic Materials:

Pupils in China, from LaRepubblica.it

It shows the interior designs solutions during pandemic outbreak it shows the acrylic Materials.

<https://buildingcue.it/rientro-scuola-settembre-divisori-plexiglas-fra-i-banchi/20291/>

-School Pupils in Italy by using clear Plexiglas dividers:

Some schools in Bergamo - the fulcrum city of the coronavirus epidemic - are preparing for the new rules of distancing: among these the Giacomo and Pio Manzù artistic high school, where **clear Plexiglas dividers** have already been placed around each desk. Plus the way of arranging the desks.

<https://www.ilmessaggero.it/scuola/plexiglass-scuola-tra-i-banchi-bergamo-liceo-ecoli-cosa-hanno-fatto-5-giugno-2020-5270710.html>

Interior designs solutions during pandemic outbreak plans Examples (Schools):

Before pandemic outbreak the interior designs solutions for schools classrooms each four students setting together.

<https://www.lakeshorelearning.com/services/complete-classrooms#21stCentury6th-8thGrade>

Seoul, South KoreaPurdue University's Plexiglas shields between instructors and students
<https://www.insidehighered.com/news/2020/06/25/wealthier-colleges-can-offer-more-protection-covid-19-cash-strapped-peers>

<https://www.voanews.com/student-union/schools-some-asian-countries-reopen-others-wait>

After pandemic outbreak the interior designs solutions

Class rooms Furniture units before pandemic outbreak:

<https://moonkids.ae/secondary-school-furniture/>

The way of furniture's arrangements was square or rectangular without social distances.

Class rooms Furniture units after pandemic outbreak:

<https://moonkids.ae/secondary-school-furniture/>

Restaurant Ideas for universities & schools:

1-Restaurant in Bangkok Thailand by using a **plastic barrier**safety screen sneeze guard.

People have lunch at the Penguin Eat Shabu hotpot restaurant that reopened after the easing of restrictions with the implementation of a plastic barrier and social distancing measures to prevent the spread of the coronavirus disease (COVID-19) in Bangkok.

<https://gulfnews.com/photos/news/eating-together-apart-restaurants-reopen-as-covid-19-lockdowns-ease-1.1589874354217?slide=4>

People have lunch in a noodle restaurant that reopened after the easing of restrictions with the implementation of a plastic barrier and social distancing measures to prevent the spread of the coronavirus disease (COVID-19) in Bangkok, Thailand.

<https://gulfnews.com/photos/news/eating-together-apart-restaurants-reopen-as-covid-19-lockdowns-ease-1.1589874354217?slide=6>

2-Restaurant in Milan Italy.

People sit in a restaurant, as shops and restaurants are allowed to reopen as Italy eases some of the lockdown measures put in place during the coronavirus disease (COVID-19) outbreak, in Milan.

Image Credit: Reuters

<https://gulfnews.com/photos/news/eating-together-apart-restaurants-reopen-as-covid-19-lockdowns-ease-1.1589874354217?slide=6>

The conclusion:

Items	Before pandemic outbreak the interior designs solutions for classrooms	After pandemic outbreak the interior designs solutions	Researchers suggestions
Interior Designs solutions :			
Interior Designs solutions :			

<u>Furniture units</u>			
<u>Furniture units</u> <u>Materials</u>	<u>Without dividers</u>	<u>With dividers:</u> 1- Plexiglas dividers 2- acrylic Materials 3- a plastic barrier	https://www.professionistiscuola.it/varie/3729-rientro-a-scuola-a-settembre-l-ipotesi-dei-banchi-con-divisori-in-plexiglass-non-piace-al-mondo-della-scuola-si-accende-il-dibattito.html <u>With dividers:</u> Antibacterial glass™ by AGC Glass Europe
<u>Flooring Materials</u>	Flooring materials other than vinyl composition tile, linoleum, or floor carpet. http://www.troubhicearena.com/DocumentCenter/View/9365/DOE-Standards-and-Guidelines?bidId=	Flooring materials other than vinyl composition tile, linoleum, or floor carpet	Antibacterial Floor PVC flooring.
<u>Wall finishes</u>	Wall paneling or wallpaper	Wall paneling or wallpaper	Antibacterial Polymer decorative panel
<u>AC System</u>	Normal	Normal	HVAC systems that use HEPA filtration can capture infectious particles, control bacteria and prevent the spread of airborne diseases to your most sensitive patients

Conclusions and recommendations:

1. Improve Air Quality is very important during the pandemic outbreak.
2. **Based on the ways that potentially infectious microorganisms can be spread in a health care environment which includes:**
 - -sneezes and coughs,
 - - Inhalation,
 - - Contact,
 - - Water mist
 - - Insect bite
 - - Airborne transmission via aerosols is important in some respiratory diseases. Aerosols are particularly dangerous because their size

The Design of Education Facilities spaces during pandemic outbreak should be changing to be with different Materials (Antibacterial materials) and the AC Systems should be change to be HVAC systems that use HEPA filtration can capture infectious particles, control bacteria and prevent the spread of airborne diseases to your most sensitive patients

3. HVAC systems can help mitigate airborne infections.

4. The architect and interior design engineer should resorted to the use of materials that did not exist before, namely antibacterial materials to use it to safe the building users during pandemic outbreak.
5. The Preparing for the new rules of distancing by using interior designs elements.
6. Antibacterial materials can be applied in the interior design of the classrooms on the walls and ceilings and some pieces of furniture where they provide safe surfaces during pandemic outbreak.
7. The international designers used different materials to achieve the social distances by using Plexiglas dividers, acrylic Materials and a plastic barrier.

Recommendations:

- 1- The necessity of researching and exploring what is new in the field of modern technology with nanotechnology and utilizing it in the field of interior design and furniture during pandemic outbreak.
- 2- The need to increase research in innovative Materials applications and alternative Materials solutions in the field of architecture and interior design to achieve The Design of Education Facilities spaces during pandemic outbreak.

References:

Published Research:

Cigdem Cetin* Zeynep Tuna Ultav† The Effects of Interior Design Parameters on the Design Quality of Nurse Stations Athens Journal of Architecture - Volume 4, Issue 2– Pages 149-170: P:156
 Heba-Talla Hamdy Mahmoud 1-Interior Architectural Elements that Affect Human Psychology and Behavior- International Journal on: The Academic Research Community Publication-p:4-http://www.ierek.com/press
 Hussein Mirna Mohammed - Design for recycling as one of the environmental requirements in product design - Journal of Architecture and Arts - Issue XI - C2 - p 714

English Books:

Reg Brown, P.E, Nicolas Lemire, P.Engand others -HVAC Design Manual for Hospitals and Clinics- Second Edition- This publication was prepared under the auspices of ASHRAE Technical Committee (TC) 9.6, Healthcare Facilities p:7-2013

Internet websites:

<https://ar.wikipedia.org/wiki/تكنولوجيا>
<https://www.archiexpo.com/prod/laminam/product-70801-2231686.html>
<https://www.archiexpo.com/prod/arconic-architectural-products-sas-merxheim-frank/product-67104-1610515.html>
<https://www.archiexpo.com/prod/pure-health/product-153885-1817573.html>
<https://www.archiexpo.com/prod/pure-health/product-153885-1816995.html>
<https://www.agc-yourglass.com/>
<https://www.gensler.com/research-insight/blog/designing-office-building-lobbies-to-respond-to-coronavirus>
<https://www.keyter.com/la-importancia-de-los-sistemas-hvac-en-los-hospitales/>
<https://www.reuters.com/article/us-health-coronavirus-netherlands-school/plastic-shields-in-place-dutch-schools-to-reopen-amid-coronavirus-idUSKBN22K242>
<https://buildingcue.it/rientro-scuola-settembre-divisori-plexiglas-fra-i-banchi/20291/>
[https://www.ilmessaggero.it/scuola/plexiglass_scuola_tra_i_banchi_bergamo_liceo_eccoli_cosa_hanno_fatto_5_giugno_2020-5270710.html](https://www.ilmessaggero.it/scuola/plexiglass_scuola_tra_i_banchi_bergamo liceo_eccoli_cosa_hanno_fatto_5_giugno_2020-5270710.html)
<https://www.lakeshorelearning.com/services/complete-classrooms#21stCentury6th-8thGrade>
<https://www.insidehighered.com/news/2020/06/25/wealthier-colleges-can-offer-more-protection-covid-19-cash-strapped-peers>
<https://moonkids.ae/secondary-school-furniture/>
<https://gulfnnews.com/photos/news/eating-together-apart-restaurants-reopen-as-covid-19-lockdowns-ease-1.1589874354217?slide=4>

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